

Category	Subcategory	Detailing	#Cited
Tools	Communication	Easy scheduling of meetings.	17
		Screen sharing with all meeting participants facilitated the lifting of business rules and documentation, since meetings can be recorded and assisted by all participants afterwards.	5
		The recorded and made available meetings within the project folders made the flow more formal, focused and professional.	3
		Email communication improved access to stakeholders (this did not exclude formal email confirmations or other means).	5
		The time to articulate the actions of analysis, clarifications, execution of the solution and availability became smaller, considering the technological facilities that the online tools allow to accelerate more and more the service.	4
		The need for all activities to be recorded by computer tools, prevented the loss of information.	8
		Questions are resolved more quickly. Just put the question on Slack and mark the responsible person who in a few minutes the person responds.	6
	Transparency	The need to manage people and processes remotely made the company investing in monitoring tools. Thus allowing greater control over what is being developed and by whom.	7
		Greater records of activities to prove remote work, such as recording, shared archiving, or sending to groups.	3
	Interaction	The use of Scrum, Kanban and Design Thinking has also contributed to better interaction among team members, especially the Product Owners with the team.	4
		Members of Agile Teams quickly adapted to remote living and made very good use of the available technological resources, with very few exceptions.	3
Collaboration	At WFH it's easier to ask for help. Sharing screens in meetings allows for collaborative help among all meeting participants.	5	
Productivity		A more rigid digital control was implemented, which enabled a more efficient monitoring of productivity.	3
		More concentration at work, not distracted by side conversations.	9
		I feel more productive by the freedom I have to manage my own time.	23